

Implementation of family rights enforcement tools

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Abstract. The issue of implementation of family rights is becoming one of the urgent problems not only in Uzbekistan, but also worldwide. Strengthening the institution of the family, which is considered the main link of society, preservation and development of family values, ensuring the rights of family members requires special attention.

In this regard, the article is devoted to today's current issues and analyzes the means of implementation and protection of family rights.

It is also explained that the protection of family rights is carried out with the help of measures provided for by the norms of other areas of law. Due to the specific features of family law, the possibility of direct application of civil legal remedies is limited, as well as the insufficient development of effective mechanisms for the institution of alternative means (for example, mediation) in resolving family disputes.

It is difficult to say that even administrative and legal instruments will be effective in the conditions of the complexity of modern family relations. In particular, the mechanisms of protection of rights in family relations with an international legal element require improvement. In the context of the development of digital technologies, new modern methods of protecting family rights, including remote court hearings and the issue of determining the legal status of electronic evidence, are gaining urgent importance.

Key words: family rights implementation means, family rights protection means-administrative legal mechanisms, mediation method, court protection.

Means of implementation of family rights appear as an important element of the modern legal system. Mechanisms for protecting the rights and legal interests of family members are reflected not only in the framework of national legislation, but also in international legal documents. In this process, the laws adopted by the state, government decisions and departmental normative legal documents become important, they create the legal basis for the regulation of family relations and provide the necessary conditions for the realization of the rights of family members.

Protection of citizens' family rights and interests protected by law is carried out in accordance with the law, that is, by applying appropriate forms and methods of protection. There are two main means of protection of rights: jurisdictional and non-jurisdictional.

Jurisdictional means of protection is the activity of bodies authorized by the state (court, prosecutor's office, guardianship and guardianship body, internal affairs body, civil

registry office, etc.) to protect violated or contested rights. The general (judicial) and special (administrative) procedures for the protection of violated rights are distinguished within the framework of jurisdictional protection.

Non-jurisdictional means of protection are the actions of citizens and organizations to protect rights and interests protected by law, which they carry out independently without referring to authorized bodies. Such actions are called self-defense of rights.

One of the main means of implementing family rights is the mechanism of judicial protection. Judicial bodies play an important role in resolving family disputes, determining the validity of marriage contracts, determining alimony obligations, limiting or revoking parental rights, and resolving adoption issues. Decisions made by courts have legal force and are binding on all state bodies, public associations and citizens, and their implementation is guaranteed by the state.

Another important tool for the implementation of family rights is the mechanism of administrative and legal protection. Guardianship and guardianship bodies, registry office bodies, prosecutor's office, internal affairs bodies and other authorized state agencies actively participate in the protection and provision of family rights. These bodies implement measures to regulate family relations, resolve disputes and prevent crimes within their powers.

Notary bodies play an important role in the implementation of family rights. They perform important functions such as approval of marriage contracts, registration of inheritance rights, approval of agreements on payment of alimony, registration of wills. Property and non-property rights of family members are legally strengthened through notarial actions, which serves to prevent disputes that may arise in the future.

The role of civil society institutions in the implementation of family rights is increasing. Non-governmental non-profit organizations, neighborhood citizens' meetings, women's committees and other public associations carry out effective activities in such directions as strengthening family relations, increasing the legal culture of family members, resolving disputes through mediation, and providing necessary legal and social assistance.

One of the modern means of implementing family rights is the institution of mediation. Mediators help resolve family disputes peacefully, taking into account the interests of the parties. During the mediation process, the parties look for ways to resolve the dispute based on mutual agreement, which will save court costs, save time and preserve family relationships.

International legal mechanisms are also important in the implementation of family rights. International agreements, conventions and agreements define universal standards for regulating family relations. Interstate cooperation will be established on the basis of international legal documents, which will allow solving cross-border family disputes, collecting alimony, and solving adoption issues.

Preventive measures have a special place in the implementation of family rights. In this, systematic work is carried out in such directions as increasing the legal consciousness and culture of family members, strengthening family values, preventing family conflicts, providing psychological and legal advice to families, and improving legal documents in the field of family relations.

These measures serve to ensure the effective implementation of family rights. The social protection system is also an important tool for the implementation of family rights. Social assistance, allowances, benefits and other social support measures provided by the state are aimed at ensuring the rights and interests of family members. Through the social protection system, necessary assistance is provided to low-income persons, persons with disabilities, large families and other needy families, which enables them to fully exercise their family rights. The main form of protection of family rights is court protection. The protection of family rights is carried out in the court procedure according to the rules of civil court proceedings, and in the cases stipulated by the Family Code, it is carried out by state bodies or guardianship and patronage bodies. The ability of family members to protect their family rights through the court is included in the basic principles of family law, which corresponds to the article of the Constitution guaranteeing the rights and freedoms of every citizen under the protection of the court.

The provision of protection of family rights is also strengthened in other laws. In particular, according to the law on additional guarantees of social support for orphans and children deprived of parental care, orphans and children deprived of parental care, Also, their legal representatives, guardians (sponsors), guardianship and guardianship bodies, and the prosecutor have the right to apply to the relevant courts in order to protect their rights.

The protection of violated or conflicted family rights is carried out in the general jurisdiction courts in the procedure of litigation or cases arising from public-law relations. The court examines and resolves disputes regarding the subjective right or interest protected by law of family members.

"In addition, decisions and actions (or inactions) of state authorities, local self-government bodies, officials, and state and municipal employees that violate certain family rights can be appealed to the court. For example, situations such as the refusal of the Civil Registration Authority to register a marriage, or the refusal of a local self-government body to allow persons who have not reached the legal marriage age to marry."

"Also, it should be noted that any citizen has the right to appeal to the Constitutional Court with a complaint about the constitutionality of a law that restricts their rights, including family rights, in their work. The grounds for citizens to apply to the court for the protection of family rights are varied, and they are usually specified in the Family Code."

"The Family Code includes matters of the most important decisions in the field of family legal relations, which fall under the jurisdiction of the court. These are as follows:

- Divorce;

- Annulment of marriage;
- Division of joint property of the spouses;
- Amendment or annulment of the marriage contract;
- Establishment of paternity and determination of the fact of acknowledgment of paternity;
- Objections to the entries in the birth register regarding the parents;
- Resolution of disagreements between parents regarding the upbringing of minor children and their place of residence;
- Exercise of parental rights by a parent living separately from the child;
- Contact of the child with relatives;
- Protection of parental rights;
- Deprivation of parental rights;
- Restoration of parental rights;
- Restriction of parental rights;
- Cancellation of restriction of parental rights;
- Recovery of alimony for children and determination of its amount;
- Parents' participation in additional expenses for children;
- Recovery of alimony from adult children for parents;
- Determination of the procedure and amount of adult children's participation in the fulfillment of additional expenses for parents;
- Alimony recovery and determination of its amount from spouses or former spouses;
- Alimony recovery from stepchildren for a stepparent;
- Recognition of the alimony agreement as invalid;
- Change of the amount of alimony and exemption from alimony payment;
- Adoption of a child;
- Change of the surname, first name, and father's name of an adopted child;
- Registration of the adoptive parents as the child's parents;
- Cancellation of adoption, and others."

"Many cases arising from family legal relations fall under the jurisdiction of judges as provided by law (except for cases concerning the dispute of paternity (maternity), establishment of paternity, deprivation of parental rights, and adoption of a child). Judges are considered general jurisdiction judges and are part of the unified judicial system.

In cases provided for by law, the protection of family rights is also carried out by state authorities. These authorities include not only executive authorities but also the prosecutor's office, law enforcement agencies, the Ministry of Justice, and educational institutions."

"The Family Code imposes an obligation on executive authorities to take measures to protect the rights and legal interests of children deprived of parental care. For this purpose, executive authorities must organize the registration of children deprived of parental care and assist in placing such children in families."

"Law enforcement agencies may participate in the compulsory enforcement of decisions related to the abduction of a child, as well as in the search for individuals who are evading alimony payments. The Ministry of Justice is responsible for cases where a husband or wife is declared deceased or presumed missing, in which case it may restore the marriage, establish paternity of a person who was not married to the child's mother based on a joint application by both the child's father and mother, and exercise other powers.

Prosecutors have broad authority in protecting citizens' family rights. Their actions to protect family rights may be expressed through the following requests to the court: declaring a marriage invalid (Article 28 of the Family Code); depriving parents of parental rights (Article 70 of the Family Code); limiting parental rights (Article 73 of the Family Code); declaring an alimony agreement invalid (Article 102 of the Family Code); annulment of adoption (Article 142 of the Family Code)."

"Additionally, regardless of the party that initiates the court case, the prosecutor is required to participate in cases regarding the deprivation, restoration, and limitation of parental rights (Articles 70, 72, 73 of the Family Code), adoption of a child (Article 125 of the Family Code; Article 273 of the Civil Procedural Code), and annulment of adoption (Article 140 of the Family Code). The prosecutor must also oversee the legality of the removal of a child from their parents by guardianship and custody authorities (Article 77 of the Family Code) and participate in other relevant cases.

The prosecutor's authority is based on the duty to ensure the protection of human rights and freedoms, as well as to protect the rights of individuals who are unable to defend their own rights due to health issues or age (such as minors), as stipulated by law. This includes taking actions such as participating in court proceedings, filing claims in court, and providing support for such claims."

"Regardless of whether the prosecutor attends the first-instance court hearing, if they are participating in the case, they have the right to submit a petition to the second instance and supervisory courts to challenge the court's decision (Articles 320, 331, 336, 337, and 376 of the Civil Procedural Code, parts 2, 1, 1, and 3 respectively).

The prosecutor (or their deputy) also has the right to submit a petition to eliminate violations of the law, issue a warning about the non-acceptability of legal violations, and file a protest against unlawful acts of administrative authorities (Articles 23-25.1, 26-28, 35, 36 of the Law on the Prosecutor's Office)."

The protection of the rights of minors left without parental care and placed in educational, medical institutions and social protection institutions is entrusted by law to the administration of these institutions. In accordance with the Model Regulations on Educational Institutions for Orphans and Children Left Without Parental Care, the main

tasks regulating the activities of the relevant state and municipal institutions include ensuring social protection and protection of the rights of those in care.

The main functions of educational institutions are, first of all, to fulfill the obligations of guardians (trustees) of those in care (Article 147 of the Family Code), as well as to notify guardianship and trusteeship bodies about the possibility of placing them in a family (Article 122 of the Family Code).

In some cases, in order to protect the interests of children (in particular, when it is impossible to execute a court decision on the case of taking a child away and transferring him to another person - Article 79 of the Family Code), their temporary placement in a foster care institution, medical institution and other similar institutions is allowed.

Officials of state bodies and other organizations are obliged to notify the guardianship and trusteeship body about the violation of the rights and legitimate interests of the child (Article 56, Clause 3 of the Family Code). Officials of educational, medical and other institutions are obliged to send information about children left without parental care in any form to the guardianship and trusteeship body (Article 122 of the Family Code).

The functions of local executive authorities and officials in protecting the family rights of citizens may be clarified. As a territorial body of local executive power, it coordinates the implementation of city and district programs for the social protection of families, orphans and children, adolescents and youth left without parental care, and directly implements the relevant district programs. Operational management, coordination and control over the activities of the relevant department is carried out by the prefect of the relevant administrative district. Carrying out executive and distribution activities, the authority, in turn, directly implements local programs for the social protection of families, orphans and children, adolescents and youth left without parental care.

The protection of family rights is carried out by guardianship and trusteeship bodies - that is, local self-government bodies that have the authority to resolve issues of local importance and are not part of the system of state authorities, but only in cases directly provided for by the Family Code. For example, in accordance with Article 121 of the Family Code, they are entrusted with protecting the rights and interests of children left without parental care, which requires them to identify, register and place such children, as well as to carry out subsequent control over the conditions of their care and upbringing (Articles 122, 123 of the Family Code). Protecting the rights of graduates of educational institutions is also an obligation of guardianship and trusteeship bodies (Article 147, Clause 3 of the Family Code).

The Family Code assigns an important role to guardianship and trusteeship bodies in protecting the rights of family members. According to Article 78 of the Family Code, when considering disputes related to the upbringing of children, regardless of who filed a lawsuit to protect the rights of the child, the guardianship and trusteeship bodies must be involved in the case by the court. The guardianship function over the child, which is

transferred to the guardianship and trusteeship bodies by court decision in cases established by law, is very important and responsible (deprivation of parents of parental rights, restriction of parental rights, termination of adoption, etc. - Articles 68, 71, 74, 143 of the Family Code). The participation of the guardianship and trusteeship body in the execution of court decisions on the removal of a child is mandatory (Article 79 of the Family Code). In urgent cases, that is, when there is an immediate threat to the life or health of the child, the guardianship and trusteeship body has the right to independently take the child away from the parents (Article 77 of the Family Code).

In general, three main forms of protection of family rights by guardianship and trusteeship bodies can be conditionally distinguished: a) making independent decisions within their powers, including granting consent (permission) to certain actions; b) submitting relevant claims to the court in a lawsuit; c) participating in court proceedings.

In some cases, the listed forms of protection of family rights by guardianship and trusteeship bodies are interconnected and complementary. For example, the deprivation of parents of parental rights is carried out by the court both upon application and with the participation of the guardianship and trusteeship bodies (Article 70 of the Family Code). The first type of powers includes the right of the guardianship and trusteeship body to give consent to:

- establish paternity only upon application by the child's father (Article 48 of the Family Code);
- parents - to change the name and surname of a child under the age of fourteen (Article 59 of the Family Code);
- the child's relations with parents whose parental rights have been restricted by a court (Article 75 of the Family Code);
- adopt a child of minor parents under the age of sixteen - in the absence of their parents or guardians (trustees) (Article 129 of the Family Code).
- The following powers of the guardianship and trusteeship body can also be included:
 - resolve disputes between the child's guardian and the child's minor parents (Article 62 of the Family Code);
 - resolve disagreements between parents on the upbringing and education of children (Article 65 of the Family Code);
 - appoint a representative to protect the rights and interests of children in case of disagreements between parents and children (Article 64 of the Family Code);
 - resolve the issue of the child's communication with close relatives (Article 67 of the Family Code);
 - conclude an agreement with adoptive parents on the placement of a child in a family (Articles 151, 152 of the Family Code).

The second type of powers includes:

- the right of the guardianship and trusteeship body to declare a marriage or an agreement on the payment of alimony invalid on the grounds provided for by law (Articles 28 and 102 of the Family Code);
- the right to demand cancellation of adoption of a child (Article 142 of the Family Code);
- the right to file a lawsuit for deprivation of parental rights (Article 70 of the Family Code), restriction of parental rights (Article 73 of the Family Code) and alimony from parents for their children (Article 80 of the Family Code). The third type of powers includes the right of the guardianship and trusteeship body to participate in the consideration of the following cases by courts:
 - declaring a marriage invalid in cases stipulated by law (Article 28 of the Family Code);
 - exercising parental rights of parents living separately from the child (Article 66 of the Family Code);
 - depriving of parental rights and restoring parental rights (Articles 70, 72 of the Family Code);
 - restricting parental rights and canceling the restriction of parental rights (Articles 73, 76 of the Family Code);
 - adopting children (Article 125 of the Family Code);
 - canceling the adoption of a child (Article 140 of the Family Code).

In accordance with Article 11 of the Law "On Prevention of Neglect and Delinquency of Minors", certain measures to protect and restore the rights and legitimate interests of minors are carried out by commissions for the protection of minors and their rights, established by local self-government bodies. In particular, they have the right to submit a claim to the court for the deprivation of parental rights of parents (Article 70 of the Family Code). The procedure for the creation of commissions for the protection of minors and their rights and the exercise of certain state powers by them is determined by legislation. It should be noted that recently the idea of creating a system of juvenile courts (i.e. family and juvenile courts) based on foreign experience has been promoted and discussed, which would protect children's rights more effectively than courts of general jurisdiction. Taking into account the experience of the activities of social institutions for the protection of the family and childhood, it is considered necessary to take a balanced and step-by-step approach to resolving this issue, focusing primarily on improving the activities of existing structures and institutions. The rights and legitimate interests of a child are protected by his/her parents (persons replacing them), and in cases stipulated by the Family Code, by the guardianship and trusteeship bodies, the prosecutor and the court (Article 56 of the Family Code). A child has the right to independently apply to the guardianship and trusteeship body to protect his/her rights and legitimate interests, and after reaching the age of fourteen - to the court. The law does not exclude citizens from self-defense of their family rights by taking actions to stop violations of rights. This form

of protection of family rights (non-jurisdictional form) is allowed in cases where the subject of family legal relations has the opportunity to legally influence the offender without the help of a court or state bodies.

Protection of family rights and legally protected interests is ensured by applying the methods of protection provided for by law. Methods of protection of subjective family rights are understood as mandatory substantive and legal measures that restore (recognize) violated (disputed) rights and influence the offender. The Family Code does not contain a list of methods of protection of family rights. They are indicated in specific norms of the Family Code in relation to certain types of legal relations. Therefore, the holder of violated family rights can use not any, but specific method (methods) of protection of his right provided for in the relevant norms of family legislation.

In turn, the methods of protection of family rights are determined by the specific features of the right being protected and the nature of the violation. For example, such methods of protection as compensation for damage and recovery of a penalty, enforcement of an obligation, as a rule, are applied in cases of violation of the property rights of subjects of family legal relations (evasion of payment of alimony to a child - Article 80 of the Family Code; occurrence of alimony debt - Article 115, Clause 2 of the Family Code). The most characteristic method of protection of personal non-property rights of subjects of family legal relations is the cessation of actions that violate the right or pose a threat of violation, change or termination of the legal relationship (restriction of parental rights - Article 73 of the Family Code; termination of adoption - Article 140 of the Family Code).

The Family Code provides for various methods of protecting family rights, taking into account the nature and type of violation, including:

a) recognition of the right (Article 30 (paragraphs 4, 5), 38, 39, 48-50, 66, 67 of the Family Code, etc.);

b) restoration of the violated right (Articles 26, 30, 44, 52, 72, 76 of the Family Code, etc.);

c) cessation (prevention) of certain actions that violate (restrict) or threaten to violate the right, including by restricting or depriving one person of his rights in order to protect the rights of another person (Articles 65, 68-71, 73, 77 of the Family Code);

d) forcing to fulfill an obligation - for example, to pay alimony (Articles 80, 85, 87, 89, 90, 93-97 of the Family Code), to compensate for material or moral damage (Article 30 (paragraph 4) of the Family Code), to pay a penalty (Article 115, paragraph 1 of the Family Code) and to compensate for losses (Article 115, paragraph 2 of the Family Code);

e) termination or change of legal relations (Articles 43, 101, 119, 120, 140-143, paragraph 2 of Article 152 of the Family Code);

e) and other methods.

The methods of protecting family rights established by the Family Code are not the same in their legal nature. In the literature, their division into protective measures and

liability measures is the most widespread, which differ from each other in the grounds for application, social purpose, functions and forms of implementation.

The greatest practical importance is that liability measures, unlike protective measures, are applied only to a person who has culpably violated a subjective right and are expressed in additional burdens on the offender in the form of deprivation of certain family rights or imposition of additional obligations on him.

Liability under family law arises only in the presence of a family offense. The mandatory elements of a family offense are the unlawful action (inaction) of the subject and his fault (the presence of harm, therefore, when it comes to the causal connection between the unlawful act and the resulting harmful consequence, these elements are not mandatory for all cases of the offense). Among the methods of protecting family rights, the following can be recognized as measures of responsibility:

- compensation for material and moral damage to a bona fide spouse in the event of a marriage being declared invalid (Article 30, Clause 4 of the Family Code);
- payment of a penalty and compensation for damage to the recipient of alimony in the event of a debt arising through the fault of the person obliged to pay alimony (Article 115 of the Family Code);
- deprivation of parental rights (Article 70 of the Family Code);
- annulment of adoption (Article 141, Clause 1 of the Family Code), etc.

Due to their diverse nature, methods of protecting family rights can in some cases be applied only by the court:

- recognition of a marriage as invalid;
- recognition of a marriage contract as invalid;
- deprivation of parental rights;
- restriction of parental rights;
- termination of adoption, etc.

In other cases, the law establishes the administrative procedure for their implementation, that is, by the guardianship and trusteeship body, the Civil Registry Office:

- dissolution of marriage in the Civil Registry Office;
- obliging the guardianship and trusteeship body not to prevent the child from communicating with close relatives, etc.

Protection of family rights is also carried out through measures provided for by the norms of other areas of law:

- civil law (for example, Article 30 of the Civil Code provides for the restriction of the legal capacity of a citizen who abuses alcoholic beverages or drugs and puts his family in a difficult situation with such behavior);
- criminal law (Articles 150-157 of the Criminal Code);
- labor law (Articles 253-263 of the Labor Code).

In order to fulfill the obligations assumed by the state to protect the family, it is envisaged to strengthen and organize special units within the social direction of executive authorities to develop and implement state family policy measures (paragraphs 15, 22 of the Main Directions of the State Family Policy), which in the future will provide for the performance of certain functions by the specified units to protect family rights.

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